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Research Article

**CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDY ON HEALTHCARE WASTE
MANAGING ROUTINES IN SIR GANGA RAM HOSPITAL,
ALLIED HOSPITAL AND MAYO HOSPITAL OF LAHORE AND
WASTAGE PRODUCTION FREQUENCY IN THESE
HOSPITALS**¹Javaid Aamir, ²Sheharyar Ahmad, ³Ali Umair¹Shalamar Medical College²Fatima Memorial Hospital³Punjab Medical College**Abstract:**

Objective: To evaluate hospitals wastage management practices around healthcare centres of Lahore, their wastage production frequency.

Study Design: Healthcare centres based evaluation study.

Place and Duration of Study: At Sir Ganga Ram Hospital, Allied Hospital and Mayo Hospital analytical survey carried out, which is started from July 2017 and ended in August 2017 for the duration of two months.

Methodology: To analyze the production and dispose off system of the Hospitals, such as particular wastage like radioactive and pathological wastage. We added the PIC and INMOL labs for analyzation from the city. We got 80 persons for this job. We made a question bank to collect information from them in accord with the knowledge about the wastage, production and disposing off wastage and practices or the administration as per 2005 rules. We gathered all the data with some other resources in respect to depend upon their information.

Results: No one out of them was using the clothes for protection while handling the wastage. There was a huge difference between the practices, which were practicing there, and the methods of healthcare wastage administration. We found 70 people out of them who were vaccinating against Hepatitis B. Most of them were sweepers and sanitary staffs, which were on the job of handling the wastage, were less than the nursing staff.

Conclusion: Hospitals wastage administration is society crisis. 2005 Rules of healthcare wastage administration hold a power, unfortunately in Pakistan, the hospitals do not pay attention to the rules and does not try to implement on them.

Key Words: Wastage Segregation, non-danger HC wastage, danger HC wastage, Hospital wastage, Hospital wastage production velocity, Hospital wastage administration, wastage recognition, Disposal of wastage.

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INTRODUCTION:

Wastage of healthcare centers is managed as per Hospital Waste Management Rules-2005. These consist of word blood bank, autopsy centre, mortuary, maternity center, veterinary institutions, a clinic, labs, treatment centre, healthiness division, pharmacy and any other capability which concerned with the biomedical and hospital activity. Hospital waste consists of all type of entity, which produced there [1]. WHO shows the Hospital wastage as all the wastage flow of hospital, urgent situation release aid, study capability and labs. Health care mechanism includes some special wastage stream; many of them need rigorous concern & dispose off [4].

Hospitals and Biomedical wastages, these come from defensive/remedial/palliative actions during monitoring, human medication analysis and veterinary. Animals and humans also produce the wastage due to vaccination, testing and studies [5, 6, 7]. Hospitals wastage may divide in 2 categories, particular / Risk Hospital wastage and common / non Risk Hospital wastage [4, 6, 8]. WHO declares that 10 percent of wastage is infectious, 5 percent is non-infectious and 85 percent is not dangerous [7]. The production quantity differs from hospitals to hospitals and country wise. In Pakistan 20% of healthcare wastage is infection risky. In America, it's about 15% and at India this ratio is 25% [8].

Analysis declares that, from all over the country the wastage of hospital is almost 2.5 lac tons per year in Pakistan [9, 10]. The wastage was not shredded; this may affect harm via contaminated sharp & virus of HIV, Hepatitis C and HBV. The procedures that do not properly dispose off the instruments enhances the chances of miss use of tools that are not for sterilization or for re using, used syringes, blood bags and IV tubes [11, 12]. Healthcare wastage organization means administration of waste collected at hospitals with these methods, these would assist to broaden the disease [5, 13]. Suitable supervision of hospitals wastage is crucial part of ecological health protection; this should be the fundamental aspect of hospital. Improper administration increases the threat to society and atmosphere. At Hospital centres wastage collectors, general people, admitted victims,

wastage dispose off staff etc suffers from chemicals, infectious wastage and other specific HCW [4].

METHODOLOGY:

Survey conducted at Services Hospital, Gulab Devi Hospital, Jinnah hospital, Institute of nuclear medicine and oncology (INMOL) and Punjab Institute of Cardiology (PIC), visited to conduct investigative studies & collect present statistics concerning administration's hospitals wastage. Tertiary medical centres contained two hundred bed, sanitary personnel & sweepers, nursing personnel, concerned with administration's wastage on different source at hospitals also added in the study. This had a comparative survey among the territory hospitals of Pakistan, which were consist of extant data informative collections. Survey took place with the hygienic personnel & sweeper conducting duty at ward, paramedical and nurses with the hospitals administrations help.

We got sample from sweeper, sanitary worker, nurse, sanitary in charge, nursing assistant. At first step, we got list of healthcare centres at Lahore from the Punjab Health division. On second step, we randomly selected five wards from each of three hospitals. On third step, we selected the five responder nursing staff & hygienic personnel out of that region. We attained the sample of eighty people.

These responders concerned with hospitals administration wastage, we investigated them and collected the data by using different type of question for collecting original feedback instead of relying on theoretical information collected through questions. Further, to avoid from this abnormality, secondary collected statistics by reading the wastage register written by nursing staff. We gathered the information through different type of question answer session. Data sorted out manually for each question and analyzed. Hospital wastage produced in grams / patient daily by every healthcare did calculate according to procedure mentioned before.

RESULTS:

Evaluation of hospitals Wastage Production Rate as per Table No 1 mentioned below part wise (P1, P2, P3).

Table-1 P-I: Hospital Wastage Initiation Ratio (Mayo Hospital)

Name of Ward, Unit-Block or Department	Wastage Initiation Ratio (Grams / bed daily)
Oncology Ward	1500
Pediatrics Ward	1090
Gynecology and Obstetrics Unit-1	1400
Gynecology and Obstetrics Unit-2	1700

Table-1 P-II: Hospital Waste Initiation Ratio (Allied Hospital)

Department, Block, Ward or Unit	Wastage Initiation Ratio (Grams / bed daily)
Surgical Ward	1500
NOT Emergency Ward	5000
Medical Specialist Wards	3650
Government Officers Block	2250
Medical Emergency Ward	1500

Table-1 P-III: Hospital Wastage Initiation Ratio (Sir Ganga Ram Hospital)

Name of Ward, Unit-Block or Department	Wastage Initiation Ratio (Grams / bed daily)
Post-Operative Ward	2000
Medical Emergency Ward	1000
Various Medical Units	1310
Private Cottages	2500
Chest Emergency & ICU	3600

It shows data on wastage production at different hospitals and their calculation. The middling hospitals wastage production velocity in HC centres had expected at 2200g / patient daily. In public zone healthcare centres, Services and Jinnah hospitals, the rate of wastage production range is among 1500 to 5000g & 1100 to 1700g / patient daily

correspondingly. In Gulab Devi centre, the total wastage production did vary from 1000 to 3600g / patient daily.

Although, medical centres wastage production tempo had high in Services Hospitals & lower at Gulab Devi centre and Jinnah healthcare centre with falling between both.

Table No 2 P-I: Educational Level of Respondents

Hospitals			Illiterate	Pre-Matric	Matric	College Level
Sir Ganga Ram Hospital	Frequency		09	01	09	06
	Percentage		36 %	04 %	36 %	24 %
Allied Hospital	Frequency		09	06	06	04
	Percentage		36 %	24 %	24 %	16 %
Mayo Hospital	Frequency		09	00	11	05
	Percentage		36 %	00 %	44 %	20 %
Total	Frequency		27	07	26	15
	Percentage		36 %	09 %	35 %	20 %

Table No 2 P-II: Training on Healthcare Waste Management

Hospitals			Received	Not Received
Sir Ganga Ram Hospital	Quantity		07	18
	Ratio		28 %	72 %
Allied Hospital	Quantity		25	00
	Ratio		100 %	00 %
Mayo Hospital	Quantity		25	00
	Ratio		100 %	00 %
Total	Quantity		57	18
	Ratio		76 %	24 %

Table No 2 P-III: Training to New Entrants

Hospitals	Given	Not Given
Sir Ganga Ram Hospital	Quantity	06
	Ratio	24 %
Allied Hospital	Quantity	25
	Ratio	100 %
Mayo Hospital	Quantity	25
	Ratio	100 %
Total	Quantity	56
	Ratio	75 %

Appraisal of hospitals Wastage Management Practices Table-2 shows the point of training and education conveyed

to all those involved in hospital wastage administration method from all hospitals. 36% staff was illiterate like Sweepers / Sanitary workers and 20% got education till college like ward boys.19% persons held the BSc education. In the survey of people, uneducated and pre-metric were more in Allied Hospital and Sir Ganga Ram than in Mayo Hospital.

Table No 3 P-I: Level of Hygiene, Safety and Protection of Respondents

Hospitals		Immunization	Use of Protective Clothing	Puncture Proof Containers Usage	Hand Washing
Sir Ganga Ram Hospital	Yes	20	25	25	25
	No	05	00	00	00
Allied Hospital	Yes	14	25	25	25
	No	11	00	00	00
Mayo Hospital	Yes	15	25	25	25
	No	10	00	00	00
Total	Yes	49	75	75	75
	No	26	00	00	00

Table No 3 P-II: Segregation & Identification of Healthcare Waste

Hospitals		Segregation	Destruction of Needles etc.	Identification (use of color-coded containers)
Sir Ganga Ram Hospital	Yes	21	25	25
	No	04	00	00
Allied Hospital	Yes	25	25	25
	No	00	00	00
Mayo Hospital	Yes	25	25	25
	No	00	00	00
Total	Yes	71	75	75
	No	04	00	00

Table number 3 showed the ratio of vaccination of hospital wastage administration employees and the usage of clothes for protection, hand wash practice and separate prick proof containers after hospitals wastage handlings in all centres. 65% persons vaccinated of Hepatitis B. sweepers did not get the vaccination of HBV. 100% respondents did claim the usage of protection clothing and washing of hands twice.

Table No 4 P-I: Occurrence of Hazard Waste Elimination / Gathering Daily

Hospitals		Once	Twice	Thrice
Sir Ganga Ram Hospital	Frequency	08	17	00
	Percentage	32 %	68 %	00 %
Allied Hospital	Frequency	12	02	11
	Percentage	48 %	08 %	44 %
Mayo Hospital	Frequency	00	00	25
	Percentage	00 %	00 %	100 %
Total	Frequency	20	19	36
	Percentage	27 %	25 %	48 %

Table No 4 P-II: Transference Method of Medical Centre Wastage Hazard

Hospitals		Hand Cart	Cart	By Hand
Sir Ganga Ram Hospital	Quantity	16	00	09
	Ratio	64 %	00 %	36 %
Allied Hospital	Quantity	07	00	08
	Ratio	28 %	00 %	72 %
Mayo Hospital	Quantity	25	00	00
	Ratio	100 %	00 %	00 %
Total	Quantity	48	00	27
	Ratio	64 %	00 %	36 %

Table number 4 showed that sixty-four percent responder sweeper 28% (7) at Services centres, 64% (16) at Gulab Devi health care centre & cent percent at Jinnah medical centre had used wheel trolley to cart of wastage held in

main baggage & container at production stage to vital cargo space depot.

DISCUSSION:

Amount of wastage generation per bed differ very much as compare to one to another hospital, state to state [8] and still inside the state [6]. Wastage production tempo depends upon the manner of the healthcare centres [8]. In Pakistan, the wastage production ratio estimated at 500 to 2500 grams / patient daily [12, 14]. According to surveys in different major and populated district showed middling generation of hospitals wastage is 1500 grams / patient daily [13]. Although, ratio of medical centres wastage production investigated during the reading had low value rather expected by urbanized nation include USA. At USA, this had the ratio of 7000 grams / patient daily. At UK, it is 2005 grams / patient daily.

Healthcare centres needs to rectify all those indulged in hospitals wastage administration must treat at equality [1]. In Gulab Devi Hospital, sweepers & sanitary staff vaccinated in opposition to HBV. Personal cleanliness is essential for minimizing the danger of managing health wastage. Conservative wash services should be given to the workers, persons cleanliness must incorporate to schooling system, healthcare centre administration legally thankful to giving the workers self-protective cloth, these consists off mask, intense job throwaway glove, work boot, legs protector [11]. Even though argue of cent percent responders concerned the usage of caring cloth, the article of helpful clothing had not used any one of them. Sad condition of dealings was, literature does speak on wastage administration practice such as transportation, collection, storage, segregation, and dispose off, but consist of protection & shield of workers concerned with these type of practice. Healthcare administration should give split stab resistant syringe container, needle, busted glass & additional prickly stuff to avoid unplanned injury to persons managing them [3,8,11,14], as spread of disease (HBV, HCV and HIV, particularly) usually occur via injury from infected sharp [4,14]. Still at Pakistan, ecological safety Act 1997 and medical centre Wastage administration Rules-2005 are quiet regarding protection and hygiene individual security, The law tells for the managing of wastage baggage and container by the sanitary staff and sweepers in an accurate approach. At all responder hospitals, we noticed, nursing team had intended for wastage separation to danger & no-danger category according to law were not practicing this rule on other hand the sweeper and sanitary personnel had extra involvement during wastage deputation. Segregation of materials into danger and non-danger category is a

key to its reduction and adequate administration [8,12,13,14]. The respective personnel were not managing the wastage with proper technique, excluding a few departments in Jinnah medical centre. According to hospitals Wastage Management Rules-2005, wastage should be collected daily in settlement with the schedule specific in wastage administration map. Detached yellowish wastage baggage & container should change with fresh [2,5,8,11,12,14]. It showed in Table number 4, statistics stated by responders in accordance with cent percent usage of wheel trolley at Jinnah medical centre was overstated 01. In fact, sweeper and hygienic personnel from ward had founded collecting wastage since baggage & container in huge carriages in fifty-liter ability. Management rule 2005 rigorously forbids the sanitary personnel/sweeper to take part in separation process of wastage [3].

CONCLUSION:

Hospitals wastage administration, of danger wastage in particularly, is a society problem, the consequences are very vast and diverse. Growing ratio of wastage production, its unprincipled separation and inappropriate disposed off for stumbling & turnaround of rising trend of general unprofessional conduct. Hospitals wastage administration is society crisis. 2005 Rules of healthcare wastage administration hold a power, unfortunately in Pakistan the Hospitals do not pay attention to the rules and does not try to implement on them.

REFERENCES:

1. Badesha JS. Hospital Waste Management -1. Bristol: Environmental Toxicology Centre, University of Bristol. 1995; p 1.
2. Kunders GD. Hospitals! Facilities Planning and Management. 3rd ed: New Delhi: Tata McGraw Hill Publishing Company Limited, 2006; pp 450-451.
3. Anonymous. Hospital Waste Management Rules. Islamabad: Ministry of Environment, Government of Pakistan: pp 01-14. [online] available from www.environment.gov.pk/act-rules/rHWMRules2005. PDF [cited 2008, September 10].
4. Johannessen LM, Dijkman M, Barton C, Honrahan D, Boyer MG, Chandra C.
5. PARN. Hospital Waste Management. Pakistan Anti-microbial Research Network: [online] available from http://www.parn.org.pk/index_files/hospitalwaste.html [cited 2008, Sept 10].

6. Park K. Preventive and Social Medicine. 18th ed: Jabbal Pur: M/S Banarsi Bhanot Publishers, 2005; pp 595-599.
7. Aktar N. Medical Waste Management: A Review. Thailand: Asian Institute of Technology. [online] available from www.eng-consult.com/BEN/papers/paper-anasima.PDF [cited 2008, September 10].
8. Srinivisan AV. Managing A Modern Hospital. 4th ed: New Delhi: Response Books, 2005; pp 299-313.
9. Government of Pakistan, Planning Commission-2005, Islamabad: Medium Term Development Framework, 2005-2010. [online] available from [www.environment.gov.pk/pub-pdf/StateER2005/Part3-Chp% 207.pdf](http://www.environment.gov.pk/pub-pdf/StateER2005/Part3-Chp%207.pdf) [cited 2008, September 10].
10. Anonymous. Hospital Based Fact Sheet. Islamabad: Environmental Pollution Unit, WWF Pakistan: p 1. [online] available from www.wwf.gov.pk [cited 2009, April 24].
11. Ilyas M. Public Health and Community Medicine. 7th ed: Karachi: Time Publishers, 2006; pp275-281.
12. Rao SKM, Ranyol RK, Bhattia SS, Sharma VR: Biomedical Waste Management: An Infrastructural Survey of Hospitals: Delhi: MJAFI: 2004; 60 (4): pp 379-382.
13. Masood S (Major). Knowledge, Attitude and Practices of Paramedics in Biomedical Waste Management in Civil and Medical Hospitals at Rawalpindi [Dissertation]. 2007-2008; pp 3-5, 11. Available from the Library of Institute of Public Health, Lahore.
14. Asghar S, Parveen S, Haq MU, Masood K: Quality System Procedure for Waste Management Plan. INM QSP-04-010 Rev: No. 00: Lahore: INMOL, 2005; pp 4,11-14.
15. Health and Waste Management Guideline Note. HNP. Discussion Paper: Washington DC: The World Bank, 2000; pp 1-4, 45-50 [online] available from siteresources.worldbank.org/health/nutritionandpopulation/Resources/281627/Johannssen-HealthCare-whole.pdf. [cited 2008, September 10].